

■ AAI23

intro

recognition //
typification

perception //
classification

case study //
discussion

team

MISIDENTIFICATION IN AI

Framing the face in-between
machine-classified & **self-perceived**
gender

+ INFO

MISIDENTIFICATION IN AI

WHY mis IDENTIFI cation

MACHINES ARE BEING TRAINED
TO **recognize** AND **react** TO
RELEVANT TRAITS OF HUMAN
IDENTITY

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01

IDENTITY

PERCEPTION

02

03

RECOGNITION

ARCHIVING

04

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Technology has built the house in which we all live. The house is continually being extended and remodelled. More and more of human life takes place within its walls, so that today there is hardly any human activity that does not occur within this house. All are affected by the design of the house, by the division of its space, by the location of its doors and walls. Compared to people in earlier times, we rarely have a chance to live outside this house. And the house is still changing; it is still being built as well as being demolished.

\\ ursula franklin,
\\ the real world of technology (1989)

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IDENTITY

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face

sensitive form ready for the **communication** of **identity**

MISIDENTIFICATION IN AI

RECOGNITION // TYPIFICATION

The **urban dimension** and the intricate social network that city fabrics weave lead to new discourse effects regarding **processes** of **identification** and practices for the attachment or **resistance** to a given community

perception // classification

MISIDENTIFICATION IN AI

Gender & Face recognition // case study

how **culture** influences the way we observe and recognize gender identity
from a **visual** perspective

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SOCIOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE

Gender description and classification is reported through visual features regardless of proximity

MISIDENTIFICATION IN AI

SEMIOLOGICS PERSPECTIVE

Almost all participants justified their classification decision through visual descriptors. This leads to the assumption that facial images can be considered as minimal discrete units of language.

OPEN DISCUSSION

Have you ever experienced **misidentification**?

How did you feel about it? Did the misidentification experience make you feel part of a non-majority group?

Did this error change your human-machine relation? If yes, how?

Based on your experience, do you have any suggestions for building more inclusive technologies?

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THANKS!

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